

Communicators of forgiveness and tolerance

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The deaths of Vargas Llosa, Pope Francis and Pepe Mujica, three universal Latin Americans, deprive the world of voices that advocated consensus. They were leaders of culture, religion, and politics who demonstrated with their works that virtues must be highlighted.

Through their books, encyclicals and messages, they communicated the difficulties of the people and also the hope that, through solidarity and responsibility, citizens can achieve justice.

They may have been on different ideological shores, but they found communion in promoting humanism at the heart of technological and scientific progress. They witnessed the electronic revolution, the birth of new information flows and the knowledge society, from where they called for closing inequality gaps around democratic models where human rights and the rights of nature are respected.

Many of his writings will live on for decades to come, providing keys to interpreting a world of artificial intelligence, geopolitical shifts, increased migration and new concentrations of wealth. In this digital age of abundant networks with little depth, generous guides are needed to teach us how to understand the future. From this perspective, researchers can analyse the texts of these three innate communicators, identify commonalities and demonstrate their critical readings.

Those who take up the legacies of Vargas Llosa, Francisco and Mujica must continue to announce in simple words how to build on forgiveness, plurality, diversity, participation, and freedom of expression.